

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and its Link to a Uniform Distribution and Conservation Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability function had to be of a linear form in an e/T power expansion in order to ensure conservation of energy, i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ evaluated to first order in e/T should yield e_1+e_2/T . This leads to $f(e) = 1-e/T$ to this order. We also showed that $f(e)f(de) = f(e+de)$ means $df/de = -1/T f$.

In this note, we wish to argue that given $f(e/T)$, one may consider it as an infinite product of $1-de/T$ terms. This interesting feature seems to be that de changes based on the value of e , namely $de = e/N$ where N tends to infinite for all e cases. Thus, we suggest that even though $f(e)$ is a product of uniform distributions, the energy increment de depends on the final value of e . In other words, there is a scaling with e . $2e$ has de increments twice the size of e . In the case of a two body scattering reaction $e_1 \rightarrow e_1'$. In other words, $f(e_1) \rightarrow f(e_1')$ such that the energy change is $e_1' - e_1$. In such a case, the extra probability factor which changes $f(e_1)$ is proportional to de increments of $(e_1' - e_1)/TN$. In other words, the two different particles interacting seem to change their energies, when described probabilistically, using different de increments. This ensures that $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_1+e_2)$ as we show.

Review of Part I

In Part I, we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is governed by:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_1+e_2) \quad ((1))$$

If one uses $e_2 = de$, then ((1)) implies that: $df/de = -1/T f$ ((2))

It also implies that $f(e)$ should inherently demonstrate conservation of energy for a power series expansion in e/T retaining only the linear term. This leads to:

$$f(e) \rightarrow 1 - e/T \quad ((3))$$

$f(e)$ and a Product of $f(de)$ s

We consider the case of creating $f(e)$ from a product of $f(de)$ s. It is known that a product of two $1-e/T$ factors leads to a conservation of energy term plus 1 plus a second order term which is dropped. If one wishes to write $f(e)$ as a product of $f(de)$'s, then one must have terms in which N (the number of factors) disappears for all powers of e . Thus, one must choose:

$$De = e/N \quad ((4))$$

In other words, the de increment depends on e in question and is not a constant value for each e . As a result:

$$f(e) = (1 - e/TN)^N \quad ((5))$$

If one considers the linear term, then one has $-Ne/TN = -e/T$ ((6a))

For the quadratic term: $\binom{N}{2} \frac{e^2}{T^2} \frac{1}{N^2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{TT}$

If one approximates $\binom{N}{2} = N(N-1)/2$ as $NN/2$ ((6b))

Similarly, the cubic term is $-\binom{N}{3} \frac{e^3}{T^3} \frac{1}{N^3} = -\frac{1}{3!} \frac{e^3}{TTT}$ ((6c))

Thus, the choice of a variable e/NT ensures that N is always removed and one obtains a function strictly of e .

To see that $df/de = -1/T f$ one may note that:

$$df/de = -1/TN \binom{N}{N} (1 - e/TN)^{N-1} \quad \text{if } N-1 \text{ is considered } N, \text{ then } df/de = -1/T f(e) \quad ((7))$$

Two Body Collisions

We suggest that ((5)) is interesting for the case of two body scattering: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$.

If e_1 changes to e_3 , then the energy change is: $e_3 - e_1$ for e_1 and $e_4 - e_2$ for e_2 . Given that e_1 and e_2 change their energies by different amounts, the above discussion suggests that viewed statistically, each obtains this change through an infinite product of linear $1 - de/T$ factors, but de is different in each case. For e_1 , it is $(e_3 - e_1)/NT$ and for e_2 , $(e_4 - e_2)/NT$.

Thus, viewing the interaction statistically, one has linear uniform probability factors linked to different de values because e_1 and e_2 change by different amounts. As one may see from only examining a product of $(1 - e_1/T)$ and $(1 - e_2/T)$, one requires that the linear term be of the form $e_1 + e_2$ and this means that in the case of N de factors for e_1 , one must have $de_1 = e_1/N$ and $de_2 = e_2/N$. Thus, it is as if one scales the de 's with e .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution must satisfy $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_1 + e_2)$, i.e. conservation of e is implicit. In Part I, we argued that this means that a power series in e/T to first order of $f(e)$ must yield a linear e/T term, specifically $f(e) \rightarrow 1 - e/T$. If one uses this idea to have $f(e)$ created from a product of $f(de)$, then if there are N factors, one must have $de = e/N$. In other words, de depends on the energy and is not a constant. We show that this allows $(1 - e/TN)^N$ to yield $f(e)$ such that N disappears from each power of e . We further argue that in a two body collision, $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, e_1 changes by $e_3 - e_1$ and e_2 by $e_4 - e_2$.

If these are different, then de_1 and de_2 are different. It is as if the various de_1 's and de_2 's which bring about the energy change statistically scale with the energy change. This allows for conservation of energy, i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_1+e_2)$.